

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

S P U B L I S H I N G

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

SHELA E. DIAZ, DM-HRM

Faculty

Negros Oriental State University

sheladiaz88@gmail.com

“FOOLISHLY MINE”

I love how it started,
But I regret how it ended.
I thought I loved you,
But sadly I didn't fully know.

You fed me with such beautiful lies,
and gave me a poisonous flower,
With a gentle smile
while your eyes fluttered.

Maybe I was blind, no I was blind.
To be with you and get trapped in your dirty mines.
I fell and let the ground swallow me,
as all you did was laugh and see.

If you were an actor you'd be a famous star.
Cause you did great acting but all you did was stab my heart.
Yes, it hurts but somehow I can't let go.
You tell me beautiful words after you leave me all alone.
How stupid, I say to myself.
How stupid I am to not let go.